

The Problem Of The Creative Personality In Somerset Maugham's Novel "The Moon And Sixpence"

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Abstract: Somerset Maugham's work "The Moon and Sixpence" talks about the problem of the creative personality and, as a result, the author takes the reader into the complex world of the human psyche, forces him to look at life with a new perspective - both with laughter and with laughter. The literary work has won the attention of a wide readership due to the fact that it deeply reveals the spiritual world of the characters and shows the possibilities of artistic words with high skill.

Keywords — creative person, society, cause and problem, mentality, influence.

INTRODUCTION

The life of the French artist Paul Gauguin is the inspiration for the story, but the character of Strickland as a solitary, sociopathic, and destructive genius is more related to a mythological version of Gauguin's life, which the artist himself developed and promoted, than the actual course of his life. The real Gauguin was a participant in the artistic developments in France in the 1880s, exhibiting his work regularly with the Impressionists, and being a friend and collaborator with many artists. Gauguin did work as a stockbroker, did leave his wife and family to devote his life to art, and did leave Europe for Tahiti to pursue his career. However, none of that happened in the brutal way of the novel's character. Maugham took inspiration from the published writings about Gauguin available at the time, as well as personal experience living among the artistic community in Paris in 1904, and a visit to Tahiti in 1914. Strickland is created as an extreme version of the "modern artist as 'genius'", who is indifferent and frequently hostile to the people around him.

The lively, clear, honest and sincere language characteristic of Maugham's works ensured that they were given and read with great interest. Everyone has a profession, a profession that they have dreamed of since they were young. He strives for that dream as long as he can. Some people get this dream, some don't. And the reader has high confidence that this dream will come true. Because they don't care about the status of their chosen profession in society, how much income it brings, and how hard it is. As you grow up, your thoughts will gradually change. The limit of dreams gradually starts to touch materiality and interest. Gradually, they count with those around them. Under the impulse of various reasons, he begins to mentally choose who he will be in the future. The senses recede. Only some brave people will take the skirt of their field of interest no matter what. It is very important to listen to the heart.

The works created by Somerset Maugham contain ample opportunities to make a person more aware of psychological moods. There are several points for research in a number of

novels devoted to the problem of ethics and aesthetics. The main characters of the writer's "The Moon and Sixpence" are the young writer and Charles Strickland. The narrator of these incidents is the prototype of Somerset Maugham.

An important theme driving this novel is the idea of the simple life versus prestige and respectability. Strickland's lifestyle living and working in London and raising children with his wife, for poverty in France and ultimately a "primitive" lifestyle in Tahiti. He is far happier in Tahiti than he ever was in London, because he is exploring his passion—painting. This theme works on another level as well. Strickland's paintings are considered by most in Europe and England to be childlike and lacking in refinement. However, in following his passion to Tahiti, he discovers that his work can be masterful.

A real person begins to realize that the well-being of society is higher than personal well-being. The ties that connect a person with humanity and society are very strong ties. The writer expressed the following thoughts about the psyche of the characters in his work and the general problems in it: "Life is extremely cruel. No one knows why he is walking in this world and where he is going. Obedience is a common trait. We should appreciate the beauty of peace. We should learn to live calmly and peacefully in life until fate finds us. It is permissible to know the value of love in ordinary people. Their knowledge is better than our knowledge.

In order for a person not to deteriorate spiritually, not to lose his hidden personality and original "me", nothing, not even time, should prevent him from making a sharp turn and making a firm decision. In the work, the writer points out the need to never be deceived by the principle of "it's too late", to get rid of the shells that immobilize a person, the boring rules, and the patterns that have become common for the masses. Strickland's concept "do not live against yourself" is analyzed throughout the work.

The plot of the novel is based on facts and events taken from the life of the great French artist Paul Gauguin. This work can be described as an example of readable and interesting literature, which creates a unity of contradictions between the

creative personality of the author and his works. Strickland's works give a person a sense of spiritual and emotional power, and his brush directs the reader's imagination to irresistible streaks, which contributes to the endless bliss of the star.

Beauty is not as big a theme as the simple life or giving up everything one has, but it does allow characters to be compared. For example, Mrs. Strickland considers Charles' paintings to be beautiful, but only as decorative pieces. She does not see the same beauty he sees, the beauty of nature, or of truth. Dirk's paintings are beautiful in the way that Mrs. Strickland sees beauty—that is, surface deep and meaningless. His view of beauty, that art must make the viewer experience what the artist experiences, offends Blanche because she believes he thinks her incapable of seeing real beauty. Strickland's goal was never fame. He just wanted to engage in the art he wanted until he was exhausted, to convey the words of his heart to people with his pictures, and in general, to leave his heart in the world forever. He managed to do it. If he wanted to be famous, he would not have liked the masterpiece he painted at the end of his life. In life, it is very important for everyone to choose the right path and overcome the obstacles on this path. Coercion either breaks the human will or makes it strong enough. After all, a person has a special love for his field of interest and is successful in that direction. A person who falls into another path and another destination lives in a state of dissatisfaction with himself and life. He broke all the threads related to real life, but he is busy creating new symbols and miracles with great power. The paintings he created are not just for viewing, but very interesting and attractive, and he has expressed himself as an honest player of nature with great passion and sensitivity. Strickland's work is full of grandeur, enthusiasm and passion. Strickland's mysteries give strength and soul to a person, whose crayon is a reader eager to see the light of the stars. It is as if God found a completely new form of expression in the chaos of the universe and created it anew with all its emotions and suffering. Nature created by man reflects his inner world. How a person looks at the world, this desire is manifested in his behavior, attitude, and the person himself looks like this. When he behaves not as he is, but as he seems, our man's mind changes and he becomes a completely different person. However, a creative person expresses his individuality as a whole. His promise of change can only come from the emptiness of his inner knowledge. Strickland would never change. "A creator or an artist tries to interpret what he sees in traffic on the basis of the 'laws of beauty.' The mysteries created by Somerset Maugham contain a wide range of possibilities in terms of revealing the psychological state of man more vividly. Similarly, the pursuit of beauty in "The Moon and Sixpence" is the main theme of the novel. If this work is essentially a realistic novel, then absolute beauty is only an imagination. Strickland's aesthetic, his passion for beauty and his belief in beauty, is an attitude that comes from a romantic, aesthetic rather than a realistic attitude. Human nature is full of contradictions, and the workings of the human mind are also unpredictable.

Strickland focused on art. It seems that he is indifferent to such sensitive feelings as love, friendship and indifference, kindness. His feelings are reflected in the pictures.

Understanding and recognition of these can only be revealed after death.

We can say that the character of the main character, Charles Strickland, a mild-mannered stockbroker who rejected everything, is illuminated as an art archetype. On the contrary, Dirk's character is the archetype of love, which he controls. Anyone who wants to put love above all else should behave like this. Their conflict with Dirk's wife, Blanche, is very interesting. Viewed in this context, the motivations for choosing Strickland (art) over Struve (love), to say nothing of Blanche, should have been the actual ending of the book with her portrayal. Strickland's paintings on the walls of his home in Tahiti, painted when he was blinded by leprosy, are unmistakably both beautiful and modest. And the final scene depicts Strickland's abandoned wife and child with potential. Based on the above points, it can be assumed that Strickland's "moon" represents the idealistic sphere of art, and the "yellow sphere", which is beauty, represents human relationships.

Although the main character of the novel, forty-year-old Charles Strickland, was originally from the world of commerce, he felt from the very beginning that he had a divine power in relation to art. On this way, he even left his family and went to Paris. Strickland was literally a god of talent, but art also demanded a good deal from him. His isolation of his wife and children and his reflection on the good deeds of his beloved Dirk Struve, who helped him in a difficult time, and at the same time his injustice towards the love of Blanche Struve, which cost him his life, are the fate of the artist. Shows how complicated it is. Strickland does not obey instincts, for him social requirements are completely irrelevant. During the work, the hero is depicted without any history - without yellow hair, but at the end of his life, he creates a perfect work of art that concerns humanity.

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